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An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: NGFR.

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We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of NGFR as a candidate gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

Citations

1. Welcher, A.A., Bitler, C.M., Radeke, M.J. and Shooter, E.M., 1991. Nerve growth factor binding domain of the nerve growth factor receptor. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 88(1), pp.159-163.